

Documentation of the Symbiotic Emperor Shrimp, *Zenopontonia rex* (Kemp, 1922) from the Central Indian Ocean Islands

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Key Points:

- Animals show Symbiotic relationships for protection, reproduction, and nutrition, often switching their hosts or species over time.
- Suheli Island, an uninhabited atoll in the Lakshadweep archipelago, features a 17 km oval lagoon, supporting diverse marine habitats.
- This study records the first occurrence of the emperor shrimp (*Zenopontonia rex*) in association with sea cucumbers in Lakshadweep, Central Indian Ocean.

Abstract

During a faunal survey of the Lakshadweep Archipelago in the Central Indian Ocean Islands, two specimens of shrimps were observed on sea cucumbers, *Theleota ananas* (Jaeger, 1833), from the north-west coast of Suheli Island, Lakshadweep. The Pontoniine shrimp, *Zenopontonia rex* (Kemp, 1922), is a common emperor shrimp of sea cucumber that was collected, identified and documented at the MTRLDST in Kavaratti, Lakshadweep. The present study reports the occurrence of a sea cucumber-associated emperor shrimp from Lakshadweep, Arabian Sea, India, for the first time. Here, we provide details on the morphology, distribution, and habitat of the species.

Keywords: Arabian Sea, Pontoniine, Symbionts, *Theleota ananas*, Lakshadweep

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1. Introduction

Associations between tiny marine decapods and other larger marine animals are widespread globally, especially in coral reefs (Marin, 2012). Decapod crustaceans like Shrimps showed symbiotic association with different invertebrates and vertebrates, including sponges, cnidarians, molluscs, echinoderms, ascidians and fish (Bruce, 1976a; Bruce, 1976b; Castro, 1988; Li, 1993; Paramasivam et al., 2022a; Prakash et al., 2015; Ross et al., 1983; Thiel and

Baeza, 2001). Shrimps and their symbiotic relationship are typically commensalism (Paramasivam et al., 2022a). Symbionts benefit from such associations by using the hosts as a hiding place from predators or mating and moulting sites or as a source of food (Antokhina and Britayev, 2020; Bauer, 2004; Duffy, 2007; Fautin et al., 1995; Jons-son et al., 2001; Ory et al., 2013; Wirtz, 1997). More than 500 species belonging to the subfamily Pontoniinae were associated with all known large invertebrates in tropical marine waters (Li and Bruce, 2006; Marin, 2012). Fifty-

one species of shrimps are known to live in association with Indo-West Pacific echinoderms (Bruce, 1982). At present, 216 species belonging to 85 genera of Caridean shrimps has documented in Indian waters (Akash et al., 2020; Jose et al., 2020; Jose et al., 2021; Kemp, 1922; Madhavan et al., 2019; Paramasivam et al., 2022b; Paramasivam et al., 2022a; Prakash and Marimuthu, 2020; Prakash and Marimuthu, 2022; Radhakrishnan et al., 2012; Samuel et al., 2016). The degree of host specificity varies among symbiotic shrimps. Some of these species are opportunists and associated with various host species, whereas others are specialists inhabiting only one species (Antokhina and Britayev, 2020). Symbiotic invertebrates do not always stay on the same host during their lifespan but may switch from one individual or even species to another (Baeza and Thiel, 2007; Bell, 1984; Britayev, 1991; Castro, 1978; De Bruyn et al., 2011; Gray et al., 1968; Grove and Woodin, 1996; Mekhova et al., 2018; Prakash and Marimuthu, 2020).

Studies have brought crucial new findings on the decapod crustacean shrimp fauna in the waters of Lakshadweep Islands (Akash et al., 2020; Baby et al., 2015; Baby et al., 2019; Bharathi et al., 2019; Jose et al., 2020; Jose et al., 2021; Kuberan et al., 2019; Madhavan et al., 2019; Paramasivam et al., 2022b; Paramasivam et al., 2022a; Prakash and Ajithkumar, 2013; Prakash and Marimuthu, 2020; Prakash and Marimuthu, 2022; Prakash et al., 2011; Prakash et al., 2015; Radhakrishnan et al., 2012; Samuel et al., 2016). Many more shrimp-echinoderm associations remain to be hidden, and much more needs to be explored for the type of symbiotic relationships involved. This paper aims to provide a new report and association involving Pontoniine shrimps and sea cucumber, based on recently collected extensive material from the Lakshadweep.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Area of collection

North-west coast of Suheli Island in the Lakshadweep archipelago, Arabian Sea of the Indian Ocean (Figure 1). Suheli Par is an uninhabited atoll island within the Lakshadweep archipelago (10° 05' N, 72° 17' E), India, with an oval-shaped lagoon of about 17 km long with 78.6 SqKm area, this lagoon include two islands (Valiyakara

and Cheriyakara) and one sand bar (Indira-Shastri), one of the potential fishing ground in Lakshadweep island, fishermen of Agatti and Kavaratti depend on this reef and lagoon for their livelihood.

Figure 1: Map showing Suheli Island and * showing sample collected site in Lakshadweep archipelago.

2.2. Collection

Holothuria *Theleota ananas* (Jaeger, 1833) were collected from a depth of 4m by SCUBA diving. Five specimens of *Theleota ananas* (Jaeger, 1833) were observed for the occurrence of associated epibionts. The holothuria were collected gently by hand picking without harming the body parts and immediately placed in zip-lock bags. On reaching the boat, symbiotic organisms were separated from the host using forceps and brushes. The host sea cucumbers were released back to the original site after photographing and recording the morphometrics.

2.3. Measurements

Body measurements of the shrimp, such as carapace length (CL), carapace width (CW), rostrum length (RL) and telson length (TL), were measured using a digital calliper.

2.4. Identification and documentation

Shrimp were identified following (Bruce, 1967) and (Marin, 2012). Specimens examined in the present study are preserved in 70% ethanol and deposited in the Marine Taxonomy Reference Laboratory of the Department of Science and Technology (MTRLDST), Lakshadweep, India.

3. Results

Two specimens of shrimp associated with the Holothurian were collected and identified, using standard references, as *Zenopontonia rex* (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Image of *Zenopontonia rex* (Kemp, 1922) - (a). lateral view of the rostrum; (b). mandible; (c). pereiopod III (d). whole animal, lateral view (e). Telson dorsal view showing posterior spines; (f) ventral view showing thoracic sternites; (g). appendix masculine; (h). Dorsal view of carapace with antennula and antenna; (i). major chela of pereiopod II.

3.1. Taxonomy

Classification:

- **Class:** Malacostraca Latreille, 1802
- **Order:** Decapoda Latreille, 1802
- **Family:** Palaemonidae Rafinesque, 1815
- **Genus:** *Zenopontonia* Bruce, 1975
- **Species:** *Zenopontonia rex* (Kemp, 1922)

Synonyms:

- *Periclimenes imperator* Bruce, 1967
- *Periclimenes rex* Kemp, 1922

Periclimenes rex Kemp, 1922: 158, fig. 25, pl. 5 (type locality – Port Blair, Andaman Islands); Barnard 1955: 47; Macnae and Kalk 1962: 95; Bruce 1982: 203.

Periclimenes imperator Bruce, 1967: 53, figs. 23–25 (type locality: Zanzibar); 1968: 1166, fig. 10; 1971: 10; 1973: 135; 1976 a: 16; 1976 b: 16; 1977: 170; 1978: 230; 1982: 204; 1991: 237; 1996: 234; Bruce and Svoboda 1993: 9, fig. 2; Stack 1994: 55, 61, pl. 3, fig. 1; Franssen 1994: 123, pl. 3 E; Li 2000: 191, fig. 242.

3.2. Materials Examined

Two male specimens (MTRLDST S001) CL 3.82mm, CW 2.64mm, RL 3.97mm, and TL 2.55mm (MTRLDST S002), CL 2.30mm, CW 1.54, RL 1.72mm and TL 0.80mm, north-west coast of Suheli Island, Lakshadweep Archipelago, India (10°4'6.87"N, 72°15'46.37"E), 4m depth, Coll. KK Idrees Babu, 10 March 2021.

3.3. Diagnosis

Carapace smooth, with antennal and hepatic teeth; hepatic teeth are well developed, epigastric teeth absent; rostrum is deep and strongly depressed; dorsal carina convex bears numerous (up to 24) teeth; ventral margin is convex, ventral teeth are absent. Antennal spine is acute and slender. Scaphocerite exceeds the tip of the rostrum; flagellum is well developed. Mandibles are robust without palp. Eyes have a globular cornea; the inferior orbital angle is bluntly produced. Abdominal somites are smooth, with rounded pleura. Pleuron of the first abdominal segment is bluntly angled anteriorly. Telson has two pairs of dorsal submarginal spines and three pairs of posterior spines. Pereiopod I has robust segments; fingers are broad, shovel-like, with spatulate cutting edges. Pereiopod II are equal and symmetrical, with robust segments; palm is slender; fingers are subcylindrical, with well-developed smooth cutting edges and densely covered with long setae; fixed finger has two large teeth in the proximal half. Pereiopod III has robust segments; dactylus has sharply curved unguis without accessory spine. Propodus is robust; posterior margin

Figure 3: *Zenopontonia rex* (Kemp, 1922) with host *Thelenota ananas* (Jaeger, 1833) original colour before preservation.

with terminal and subterminal spines. Pleopod are of normal shape; the endopod of pleopod I have a subterminal triangular lobe on the distal half at the median border; proximal half bears some hook-like setae with long simple setae. Appendix masculina has four terminal setae. Uropods are normal, exopod with disto-lateral spine; well developed di-aeresis is present.

3.4. Colour in Life

The basic colour of this shrimp is orange-yellow to orange-red, with purple antennal plates, claws and walking legs, and white chromatophores in the skin covering much of the dorsal surface and tail fan. The colour of the shrimp varies depending on their host (Figure 3).

3.5. Distribution

Zenopontonia rex is native to the tropical Indo-West Pacific region. Its range extends from the Red Sea, Réunion and Mayotte to Hawaii, French Polynesia, southern Japan, New Caledonia and northern Australia (Bruce, 1967; Fransen

and Goud, 2000; Marin, 2012) Andaman Islands (Barnard, 1955; Bruce, 1982; Macnae and Kalk, 1962) and Vietnam (Bruce, 1993). Now, the occurrence is reported from Lakshadweep, Arabian Sea, India.

4. Discussion

This study provides the first record of a symbiotic shrimp *Z. rex* associated with sea cucumbers in the Arabian Sea, Lakshadweep. Sea cucumbers can be hosts for many commensal organisms, both ecto- and endo-commensals. The impact of symbionts on hosts determines the type of their interactions, and many of these associations are poorly understood (Britayev and Lyskin, 2002). The specimen collected from sea cucumbers during the present study matches the characteristics of *Periclimenes imperator* (Bruce, 1967), which is now considered a junior synonym of *Zenopontonia rex* (Kemp, 1922). Emperor shrimp, *Z. rex*, was recorded in association with more than 29 species of various invertebrates from different phyla (Antokhina et al., 2012; Fransen and Goud, 2000; Marin, 2012).

Studies on the Symbiotic association with sea cucumbers in Lakshadweep with special reference to Shrimps, crabs and polychaetes are scanty except for a few studies (Alcock, 1899; Dev Roy and Nand, 2005; Marudhupandi et al., 2014; Prakash et al., 2011; Thomas, 1969).

The present collection was made from the lagoon at 4 meters depth. Published reports on the distribution of this species show that the distribution depth of this species ranges up to 40 meters (130 feet). Living in association with large sea cucumbers, the study confirms the distribution of *Z. rex* in the Arabian Sea. This present distribution record fills the gap in the occurrence of *Z. rex* in the Central Indian Ocean islands. The earlier studies (Barnard, 1955; Bruce, 1967; Bruce, 1982; Fransen and Goud, 2000; Macnae and Kalk, 1962; Marin, 2012) recorded the distribution of the species in the Indo-West Pacific region of Red Sea, Réunion and Mayotte to Hawaii, French Polynesia, southern Japan, New Caledonia and northern Australia, Vietnam and the Andaman Islands.

5. Conclusion

This species has not been previously recorded from the Lakshadweep Islands. The morphometric characteristics of *Zenopontonia rex* agree well with the description by Bruce, 1967 and Marin, 2012 with the following features: number of rostrum teeth and number of telson spines. Previous records have reported the association of this species with the large nudibranch, sea stars and sea cucumbers. The present paper suggests that detailed studies be carried out to understand the distribution of this associated shrimp in Lakshadweep water.

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Author Contributions

IB collected the specimens; MPC conceived the study, identified the specimens and drafted the manuscript; IB and SK participated in the identification of species, design and coordination of the survey and preparation of this article. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

We declare that we have no known competition for financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article, and there is no conflict of interest between us or with other researchers in our institution or with any other institutions working in the same region and topic.

Data Availability Statement

The specimen used in the study is deposited in the reference collection, and the material is available for examination. All data collected during this study are included in the manuscript.

Ethical Approval

Since no animal experiments were conducted for this study, all applicable international, national, and/or institutional guidelines for the care and use of animals were followed.

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